

HOW TO ORGANIZE EFFECTIVE INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mustaqil ta'lim – muayyan fandan o'quv dasturida belgilangan hamda o'quvchi tomonidan o'zlashtirilishi lozim bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni shakllantirishni, o'zlashtirish darajasini amalga oshiriladigan ta'lim shakllaridan bo'lib, o'qituvchi maslahati va tavsiyalari, bilimlar taqsimotiga tayyorgarligi asosida sinfdan tashqarida bajariladi. Ushbu maqolada mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish yo'llari haqidagi ma'lumotlar jamlangan bo'lib, bugungi kunda mavjud materiallar asosida shakllantirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mustaqil ta'lim, o'quvdasturi, ko'nikma darajasi, elektronkonspekt.

ANNOTATION

Independent learning is a form of learning which is defined in the curriculum of a particular subject, and the formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies which are acquired by the student, and it is also a form of learning that takes place outside the classroom on the basis of the teacher's advice, recommendations, and preparation for the distribution of knowledge. This article provides information on how to organize independent learning, based on the materials which are available today.

Keywords: Independent learning, curriculum, skill level, e-synopses.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Самостоятельное обучение - одна из форм обучения, при которой осуществляется формирование и овладение уровнем знаний, навыков и умений, определенных в учебном плане по конкретному предмету и которыми должен

овладеть учащийся, осуществляется вне аудиторных занятий на основе рекомендаций. и рекомендации, готовность к распространению знаний. В данной статье обобщена информация о способах организации самостоятельного обучения, и она сформирована на основе доступных на сегодняшний день материалов

Ключевые слова: самостоятельное обучение, учебная программа, уровень квалификации, электронное резюме.

INTRODUCTION

The task of independent research and study of knowledge according to the requirements of the state education standard is one of the most urgent problems today. For this reason, the theoretical foundations of sciences are mastered at the level of practical skills.

The role of independent education is incomparable [1, 2]. Students are given methodical recommendations by science teachers regarding independent education. Based on the nature of science, independent education types - colorful and different electronic forms - are developed by the science teacher. Pupils listen to teachers' lectures in classrooms. Outside the classroom, the student prepares for classes, summarizes literature, and completes homework assignments. In addition, in order to study some topics more widely, he prepares abstracts by reading additional literature and solves tests on the topic. The results of independent education are evaluated based on the rating system. The purpose of the research is to identify and analyze the ways of organizing independent education among students using various sources.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the book "Biology Teaching Methodology" by J. O. Tolipova and A. T. Gofurov on the organization of independent education in students, it is necessary to develop the skills of independent and creative thinking in students. Thought is a spiritual human quality that constitutes human activity, his self, power and knowledge

[1 2, 4]. Organizational tasks of students' independent education consist of the following: 1) acquiring the skills of mastering new knowledge independently; 2) searching for necessary information, identifying convenient methods and means of learning; 3) effective use of information sources and addresses; 4) work with educational and scientific literature, regulatory documents; 5) work with electronic educational literature and data bank; 6) targeted use of the Internet; 7) determining the rational solution of given tasks; 8) database analysis; 9) systematic and creative approach to tasks; 10) being able to independently obtain scientific information in classrooms; It is the ability to defend a practical task and independent work between the trained teacher and the students of the group.

Preparing the ground for students' intellectual development and forming critical and creative thinking in this process is considered a priority in organizing independent education. The laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "On the National Program of Personnel Training" are the basis for the improvement of the higher education system in Uzbekistan. They are aimed at forming a new generation of personnel who have a high general and professional culture, who are creative and socially active, who can act independently in socio-political life, who are able to set future-oriented tasks and solve them. As in any society, in the development of our republic, the training of qualified specialists who can withstand competition in the conditions of the market economy is of great importance. After all, the importance of the expert personnel factor in the development of society is a fact of life that does not require proof. In recent years, extensive work has been done and is being done on the training of specialist personnel, improving their professional quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is being paid to developing qualities such as independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, and activity of trained specialists. As stated in the National Program of Personnel Training, "...individualization of study, independent learning and development and mastering of distance education system technologies and tools" is required. On the basis of our pedagogical activities in the higher education system and

the study and analysis of the creative work of modern teachers, targeted research dedicated to the improvement of the content of their practical and creative training and teaching methods is confirmed, so that today, in the training of highly qualified teachers there are several inconsistencies and contradictions.

RESULTS

The formation of independent learning skills plays a key role in students' acquisition of in-depth knowledge and skills from specialty, specialization or general professional subjects in the educational creative training system. The skills of independent learning include the ability to work independently with their studies, complete independent practical tasks, and defend completed independent tasks in front of teachers and students.

DISCUSSION

Organization and management of students' independent educational activities. The only way to form students' independent activity is to organize and manage their independent educational activities. Organization of independent education in the process of creative preparation of students should be carried out continuously and organically. In our opinion, to achieve a high result in this direction, in the educational process, in particular, in lectures and practical creative activities, the formation of interest in strengthening the learned educational material in students, the capacity of educational information in textbooks and supplements It is based on creating enthusiasm for expansion based on reading independently of literature. It is important to ensure that future specialists develop into fully mature, educated, independent thinking, sought-after personnel, and to use new pedagogical and information technologies that direct them to work on themselves in the educational process. The initial research on ensuring that the technological approach to the educational process, i.e., the educational process has a reproducible description as a production process, was carried out by American pedagogues in the 50s of the last century. In particular, the phrase "teaching technology" was first used by the American scientist Skinner.

CONCLUSION

The formation of independent learning skills plays a key role in students' acquisition of in-depth knowledge and skills from specialty, specialization or general vocational subjects in the educational creative training system. In the process of creative preparation of students, organization of independent education is carried out continuously and organically. The student can work with electronic educational literature and data bank. By organizing independent education, we will form a mature, knowledgeable, independent thinking, inquisitive generation.

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